

The difference between hands in the perception of the stiffness of virtual elastic objects

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Abstract. Estimating the stiffness of an object, such as when choosing a ripe fruit, is usually done by probing it with our hands. Most of the studies of stiffness perception focused on unimanual interaction with objects, but many daily interactions are performed with both hands. Here, we studied stiffness perception during interaction with virtual elastic objects touched by different hands. Participants probed pairs of virtual elastic objects sequentially using two haptic devices and reported which object felt stiffer. They either touched both objects with the same hand or touched each object with a different hand. In the first experiment, when they continuously interacted with each object, we found that right-handed participants perceived objects touched with the left hand harder than objects touched with the right hand. In the second experiment, to simulate realistic contact with objects, participants could break contact with the elastic object several times before switching between objects. In this experiment, the differences in perception were heterogeneous. Some participants perceived objects touched with the left hand harder, and some perceived them as softer than those with the right hand. These findings have substantial implications for bimanual haptic interfaces.

Keywords: Bimanual interactions · Stiffness perception · continuous interaction.

1 Introduction

When interacting with elastic objects, our sensorimotor system integrates sensory information to form a representation of their stiffness. For example, physicians estimate stiffness to determine the healthiness of a tissue. Most stiffness perception studies focused on right-handed unimanual interactions, but in real life, we use both hands to interact with objects [1]. Motor control studies have focused on two types of bimanual interactions: (1) uncoupled control, in which the two hands act separately in manipulating different objects, and (2) coupled control, in which the two hands cooperatively manipulate the same object [2]. However, before these types of interactions can be studied in the context of the perception of stiffness, we have to quantify the differences between the hands in unimanual sequential interactions with elastic objects. A previous study on the perception of stiffness during unimanual interactions [3] found differences in perception between continuous interaction with objects compared to breaking contact with the object and crossing its boundary. In this study, we set out to understand the difference in stiffness perception between hands in continuous and non-continuous interaction with the object.

2 Methods

In experiment 1, we studied continuous interactions with virtual elastic objects, and in experiment 2 we studied more realistic interactions where participants could break contact with the objects. In both experiments, we used a two-alternatives forced choice (2AFC) paradigm, in which right handed participants interacted sequentially with two elastic objects, and had to decide which object had a higher level of stiffness. Participants sat in front of a virtual reality experimental setup (see representative image). They held two Geomagic TouchX haptic devices, one in each hand. During the interaction with the elastic objects, one of the haptic devices generated force feedback $f(t)$ [N] that was proportional to the position of the participant’s hand $y_{\text{hand}}(t)$ [m] according to:

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} k[y_{\text{hand}}(t) - y_0], & \text{if } y_{\text{hand}} < y_0 \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In experiment 1, the participants (N=13) could not break contact with the object since the object’s boundary was set outside of the reachable position at $y_0 = 1.5/k$ where k [N/m] is the object stiffness level. In experiment 2, the participants (N=20) could break contact with the elastic object, and the object boundary was set to $y_0 = 0$.

In each trial, participants probed two elastic objects sequentially: a standard object ($k = 85$ N/m) and a comparison object (k chosen out of eight possible values between 40 and 130 N/m). Each participant interacted with 8 training pairs and 256 test pairs of objects in four conditions. In two conditions, they touched each object with a different hand: the standard object was explored with either the left or right hand, and the comparison object was explored with the other hand. These conditions were pooled into a single different hand (DH) condition. In the other two conditions, they touched both objects with the same hand: left (LL condition) or right (RR condition). After interactions, they reported which object felt stiffer. Based on their answers, we fitted a sigmoid psychometric function: in the same hand conditions to the probability of the participant choosing the comparison object as stiffer as a function of the difference between the comparison and the standard stiffness levels, and in DH condition, to the probability of choosing right hand touched object as a function of the difference in stiffness between the objects touched with the right and the left hands. We then extracted the Point of Subjective Equality (PSE) to quantify the bias in perception [3]. To analyze the difference between conditions, we fitted a one-way repeated measures ANOVA model: PSE as a dependent variable and the probing condition as the independent factor.

3 Results and Discussion

The participants perceived the stiffness of objects differently when touched with different hands. The direction of the bias between hands depended on the experiment. In experiment 1 (Fig. 1A), the DH curve is shifted to the right (positive PSE), indicating that the objects were perceived as harder when touched with the left hand compared to when touched with the right hand. This difference was observed for most (9 out of

Fig. 1. Experimental results. A) Example of psychometric curves of one participant in Exp.1. Black curves represent RR (dashed) and LL (solid) conditions and the red curve represent the DH condition. B) Mean PSE for the three conditions in Exp.1. The participant’s 3 PSE values from A are connected by the bold dark grey line. C-D) Examples of psychometric curves of two participants in Exp.2 with the same (C) and opposite (D) trend as A. E) Mean PSE for the three conditions in Exp.2. The participant’s 3 PSE values from C are connected by the bold dark grey line and from D by the darker grey line. Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval of PSE.

13) of the participants (Fig. 1B) with no bias in perception in the remaining 4 (their PSE was around the RR condition results). The average effect of the difference between hands in the DH condition was statistically significantly different from RR condition ($t_{24} = 5.74, p < 0.001$) and from LL condition ($t_{24} = 4.69, p < 0.001$).

In contrast to this clear direction of bias, in experiment 2, the directions of the difference between hands were inconsistent between participants. 10 participants perceived objects as harder with their left hand (Fig. 1C), 4 perceived objects as harder with their right hand (Fig. 1D), and 6 showed no bias between hands. When averaged (Fig. 1E), the difference between hands was zero because both trends cancel each other and there was no statistically significant difference between the conditions ($F_{2,38} = 0.65, p = 0.53$).

These results could be considered in the design of bilateral bimanual controllers for teleportation systems, where different information could be presented to each hand.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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